

The Schrodinger Equation, Internal Temperature and Fisher Information

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Feb. 21, 2019

In this note, we consider the time-independent Schrodinger equation written in terms of Fisher information density and internal temperature. We note, that for the ground state oscillator case, Fisher information density becomes proportional to entropy density and internal temperature becomes a constant. This leads to an equation which is consistent with the maximization of entropy (for this special case) and leads to classical statistical mechanical results. If one tries to generalize to potentials other than the oscillator, one obtains a theory completely different from quantum mechanics, namely classical statistical mechanics. (For the oscillator potential, however, the two have the same form.) Finally, we note that the form of temperature as a function of x , obtained from Boltzmann transport considerations equals the extremization of Fisher information density.

Fisher Information

Fisher information for a one dimensional problem can be defined as (1):

$$F_x = \int dx \, d(x) \left[\frac{d}{dx} \ln\{d(x)\} \right]^2$$

$d(x)$ is the spatial density, which in quantum mechanics is $W(x)W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the real wavefunction for a bound state. The presence of $\ln\{d(x)\}$, is suggestive of $d(x)=\exp(2g(x))$. Density is positive, but $W(x)$ can be positive or negative. Let us consider cases of $W(x)$ positive for all x for the time being so that $W(x)=\exp(g(x))$. (The ground state of the harmonic oscillator is one case where this holds). In fact, $W(x)>0$ may apply to various ground states as higher energy states sometimes develop positive and negative humps.

Next, note that the definition of temperature from Boltzmann transport theory (2) is:

$$T(x) = .333 \, m \langle |v - u(x)|^2 \rangle$$

We use the quasiparticle picture of (3) with a probability of $W(x)$ $\propto \sin(px)$ where $W(x) = \sum_p \sin(px)$ and $u(x) = \{ \frac{d}{dx} W(x) \} / W(x)$. (Note: In (1), a similar definition is used except for a complex $W(x)$. We use $\frac{d}{dx} W(x)$ because $\frac{d}{dx} d(x) = 2 W(x) \frac{d}{dx} W(x)$).

Then, using $W(x)=\exp(g(x))$ yields:

$$T(x) = .333 \, m \left\{ \left(\frac{d}{dx} \right) \left(\frac{d}{dx} g(x) \right) \right\} \quad ((1))$$

Next consider the time-independent Schrodinger equation with $W(x)=\exp(2g(x))$

$$(-1/2m) \{ [d/dx g(x)]^2 + (d/dx)(d/dx) g(x) \} = (E-V(x)) = .5m v(x)^*v(x) = \text{classical kinetic energy} \quad ((2))$$

The left hand side of equation ((2)) can be written in terms of Fisher information density and temperature $T(x)$ if one multiplies both sides by $d(x)=W(x)W(x)$. This yields:

$$C1 \text{ (Fisher density)} = C2 d(x) T(x) + .5m v(x)^*v(x) d(x) \quad ((3))$$

Here Fisher density is proportional to $d(x) [d/dx g(x)]^2$

Thus, the time-independent Schrodinger equation can be written in terms of Fisher density, temperature as a function of position and classical kinetic energy as a function of position.

It should be noted that Fisher density has been associated with the quantum kinetic energy term in the Schrodinger equation in the literature (5), but in this note we try to associate it with a temperature function $T(x)$. In the last section of the note, we try to show that $T(x)$ is proportional to the extremization of the Fisher information density.

Special Case of a Ground State Oscillator

In (3), it was noted that $T(x)=\text{constant}$ for the ground state quantum oscillator. This is interesting because T is constant for classical statistical mechanics. Furthermore, momentum and spatial quantum densities are of the form $\exp(-bp^*p)$ and $\exp(-ax^*x)$ which matches classical statistical mechanics. In (4), it was noted that for the ground state oscillator $V(x)d(x)$ has the form of entropy density and so for this case, the time-dependent Schrodinger equation has the form of an extremization of entropy density subject to constraints.

For the case of a ground state oscillator with $W(x) = C \exp(-ax^*x)$, we see that Fisher density is proportional to entropy density i.e.

$$d(x) \{d/dx \ln(d(x))\}^2 \text{ is proportional to } d(x) \ln[d(x)]$$

Thus, ((3)) has the appearance of an extremization problem for the quantum oscillator ground state. To see this note that:

$$C3 d(x) \ln(d(x)) = C2 T d(x) + .5m v(x)^*v(x) d(x)$$

One can divide $d(x)$ from both sides. Here T , the temperature is a constant proportional to a . Then, the solution satisfies an extremization of entropy subject to constraints.

Specifically one finds that $-d(x) \ln[d(x)] = d(x) \{E+T-V(x)\}/ C$ from ((3)), consistent with the well-known $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ of statistical mechanics.

Thus, for the special case of the ground state oscillator, one has $T(x)=\text{constant}$ and maximization of entropy. One might suggest a theory based on these ideas. It would no longer match quantum mechanics (except in the special case of $V(x)=ax^2$), but it would be consistent with classical statistical mechanics. Thus, in (4) it was suggested that classical statistical mechanics might be derivable from quantum mechanics.

Extremization of Fisher information density

Given that Fisher information becomes proportional to entropy density for $V(x)=ax^2$, and that this leads to density satisfying the extremization of entropy density subject to constraints, one may see if the extremization of Fisher information leads to any interesting results.

Consider extremizing $\exp(2g) \int [d/dx g(x)]^2$ i.e. Fisher density
This yields:

$$4 \left\{ \exp(2g) \left[2 \frac{d}{dx} g(x) \right]^2 - 2 \frac{d}{dx} \left\{ \exp(2g) \frac{d}{dx} (g) \right\} \right\} = 8 \exp(2g(x)) \left(\frac{d}{dx} \right) \left(\frac{d}{dx} \right) g(x)$$

This is, however, proportional to $d(x) T(x)$ where $d(x)$ is the density and $T(x)$ the temperature. Thus, the quantum kinetic energy $[(-1/2m) (d/dx)(d/dx) W(x)] / W(x)$ is equal to:

C1 Fisher information density + C2 extremization of Fisher information density,

Here Fisher information density is proportional to $\{[d/dx W]/W(x)\}^2$ which we call $u(x)*u(x)$, a collective velocity (not $v(x)$ the classical velocity) which was used in the calculation of temperature. In (1), which uses complex wavefunctions, the author equates Fisher information with $(4/\hbar^2) [\langle P^2 \rangle_{\text{quantum}} - \langle P^2 \rangle_{\text{classical}}]$ with $P_{\text{classical}}$ proportional to $(d/dx W)/W - (d/dx W^*)/W^*$. This seems to be a different approach than that used here. Furthermore, the author of (1) shows that quantum mechanical density satisfies a classical continuity equation. For a bound state $P_{\text{classical}}$ from (1) becomes 0.

The latter being equal to a constant times $T(x)$, the temperature as a function of x .

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems possible to write the time-independent Schrodinger equation in terms of Fisher information density and temperature as a position of x . For the case of $V(x)=ax^2$, temperature becomes a constant and Fisher information proportional to entropy density. In such a case, the time-independent Schrodinger equation is equivalent to an extremization of entropy density subject to constraints and classical statistical mechanical results are obtained. In fact, one could establish a theory generalized to other potentials $V(x)$ with T constant. This would no longer be quantum mechanics, but would be generalized classical statistical mechanics. Finally,

we note that $T(x)$, the internal temperature as a function of x is proportional to the extremization of Fisher information density.

References

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